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Artificial Intelligence Driven System Development for Educational Sign Language Translation

MASTER'S THESIS

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HALLGATÓI NYILATKOZAT

Alulírott *Dancsó Marcell*, szigorló hallgató kijelentem, hogy ezt a diplomatervet meg nem engedett segítség nélkül, saját magam készítettem, csak a megadott forrásokat (szakirodalom, eszközök stb.) használtam fel. Minden olyan részt, melyet szó szerint, vagy azonos értelemben, de átfogalmazva más forrásból átvettem, egyértelműen, a forrás megadásával megjelöltem.

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Budapest, 2025. december 12.

Dancsó Marcell
hallgató

Kivonat

Annak ellenére, hogy a természetes nyelvfeldolgozás és a jelnyelvfelismerés terén jelentős előrelépések történtek, a nagyjából 1,5 milliárd fős siket és nagyothalló közösség számára továbbra is hiányoznak a hatékony fordítási megoldások. BSc Szakdolgozat munkám pózbecslési algoritmusok és hagyományos neurális hálózati architektúrák alkalmazását vizsgálták ezen a területen, azonban a kézmozgások összetett dinamikája, ahol az ízületek hatással vannak egymásra, különleges kihívást jelent.

Kezdetben az egyes kézpózokat hagyományos módszerekkel, például MLP alapú megközelítésekkel osztályoztam. Ebben a folytatólagos kutatásban, ugyanezeket a pózokat gráf neurális hálózatokkal, azon belül: GCN és GAT architektúrák alkalmazásával osztályozom, ahol a kéz ízületeit csomópontokként modellezem, az ezek közötti kapcsolatok pedig az ízületek közötti függőségeket tükrözik. Az ujj betűzés fordításához, amely korábban transzformer architektúrát használt egy konvolúció alapú “embedding” réteggel a póz sorozatokhoz, most egy egyedi gráf alapú embedding réteget tervezek. Ez várhatóan hatékonyabban képes megragadni a kézmozdulatok relációs szerkezetét, miközben továbbra is kihasználja a transzformer modellt a szekvenciális adatok feldolgozásához.

A kutatás célja annak a hipotézisnek az igazolása, hogy a GNN-ek bizonyos körülmények között, például bonyolult jelnyelvi pózok esetén, ahol az ízületek erősen függenek egymástól, felülmúlhatják a hagyományos módszereket. Ennek teszteléséhez először több GNN architektúrát valósítok meg, majd átfogó kísérleteket végzek azok teljesítményének mérésére. A fordítás pontosságát és a feldolgozási sebességet a korábbi modellekkel hasonlítom össze.

A dolgozat második részében megvizsgálom az új megközelítés gyakorlati használhatóságát android környezetbe integrálás segítségével. Figyelembe véve a számítási hatékonyságot és a különböző jelnyelvi dialektusok közötti skálázhatóságot, újszerű, a feladatra optimalizált gráf alapú modellt hozok létre. Az elkészülő alkalmazás célja egy elérhető platform létrehozása, mely segíti a vizuális gesztusokon alapuló nyelveket elsajátítani, illetve fordítani.

Abstract

Despite advancements in natural language processing and sign language recognition technologies, effective translation solutions for the deaf and hard of hearing community, comprising approximately 1.5 billion [47] individuals globally, remain elusive. Previous work explored pose approximation algorithms and conventional neural network architectures to improve translation accuracy. However, the complex dynamics of hand movements, with joints influencing one another, continue to pose a unique challenge.

Formerly, in my BSc Thesis, individual hand poses were classified using traditional methods, such as multilayer perceptron-based approaches. In this follow-up work, I propose classifying the same poses using Graph Neural Networks (GNNs), specifically the GCN and GAT architectures, to model the hand as a graph where each joint acts as a node and the connections between them represent joint dependencies. For translating fingerspelling sequences, previously relying on a transformer architecture with a convolution-based embedding layer for pose sequences, I now introduce a custom graph-based embedding layer. This layer is designed to capture the relational structure of hand movements more effectively while still utilizing the transformer model for sequential data processing.

This research aims to validate the hypothesis that GNNs can outperform traditional methods under specific conditions, such as complex sign language poses where joints are highly dependent on each other. To test this hypothesis, I will design and implement several GNN architectures, followed by comprehensive experiments to measure their performance. Metrics such as translation accuracy and processing speed will be compared with prior models.

In the second part of the thesis, I will explore the practical usability of this approach by integrating some of the models into an Android environment. Considering challenges like computational efficiency and scalability across diverse sign language dialects, I present a new graph model, optimized for the problem. Ultimately, the goal is to create an accessible platform that helps with visual gesture-based language learning and translation.

Chapter 1

Introduction

In recent years, we have achieved remarkable breakthroughs in the field of natural language processing (NLP). With today's "voice-to-text" models, we can interact with our devices diversely and naturally. Coupled with the revolutionary advancements of large language models, we can now employ virtual assistants, access the world's knowledge through chat interfaces, and even unlock the possibility of seamless communication between any two languages. However, one unfortunate limitation of these systems is that they are available only in traditional spoken languages. While the technology seems ready, no substantial system supporting sign languages has yet emerged. Translating sign language into text would open up communication for approximately 70 million people [44], allowing them to interact with smart devices in their language, not to mention facilitating communication with those who don't know how to sign. It would also greatly assist in the education of individuals who, despite living with hearing impairments, do not have access to sign language education due to a lack of financial resources or learning tools. This group is surprisingly larger in many countries than the number of people who can sign, highlighting the complexity of the language and the challenge of this task.

1.1 Fundamentals of Sign Language

Sign language is a visual, gesture-based language used by both deaf and hearing communities for communication. Unlike spoken languages, meaning is conveyed through hand movements, facial expressions, and body posture.

Contrary to popular belief, sign language is not universal; many distinct versions exist worldwide, each with its structure. For instance, American Sign Language (ASL) and British Sign Language (BSL) are so different that they are mutually unintelli-

gible, even though both countries speak English. This is because, ASL is rooted in French Sign Language [43], while BSL evolved independently [42]. Furthermore, like spoken languages, sign languages also have dialects and regional variations, which adds further complexity to the development of intelligent solutions.

1.2 American Sign Language

American Sign Language (ASL) is used by the deaf communities in the United States and Canada. Its history dates back to the 19th century when Thomas Gallaudet and Laurent Clerc founded the first school for the deaf in the US [43]. The language used in this school combined local American sign language with French sign language, forming the foundation of ASL.

This study will focus solely on ASL, as it is the most accessible in terms of well-established datasets and knowledge about the language. It's important to note, however, that the models and algorithms developed for sign language datasets are often universal, regardless of which sign language they are applied to.

1.3 Fingerspelling

A subset of most sign languages is fingerspelling (FS), where hand shapes represent letters. In some sign languages, FS is commonly used to convey names, foreign words, or specialized terms that don't have their own signs. In other languages, fingerspelling is used less frequently, with signers preferring complete phrases and sentences. Additionally, there are smaller sign languages around the world, which have developed in unique communities and are not influenced by the larger, more widely used sign languages. An example is Kolok Kata [35], native to two neighboring villages in northern Bali, Indonesia. Interestingly, Kata Kolok has no official FS system, demonstrating that FS is not essential for sign languages to function. These smaller languages often reflect the culture and history of the community in which they developed.

Like many other sign languages, ASL includes FS, which is frequently used for names, addresses, phone numbers, and other information commonly typed on a mobile phones. Many deaf smartphone users find FS faster than typing out words, hence being significantly faster than typical virtual keyboard typing, averaging 57 words per minute compared to the 36 words per minute in the US [6]. In ASL, the alphabet and numbers are communicated using just one hand, unlike BSL, which

requires both hands. While other gestures, like head movements or leaning forward, can add emphasis during fingerspelling, the letters themselves can be recognized solely by observing the dominant hand. FS thus serves as a useful foundation for translating more complex gestures that rely on facial expressions, head movements, and additional gestures to convey meaning.

Figure 1.1: Extended ASL alphabet.¹

1.4 Taxonomy of Sign Language Translation

In sign language translation, three primary approaches are distinguished based on input and output types. The first approach, known as static or isolated, processes discrete units and relies on single snapshots, such as a static image as input or an individual predicted sign as output. The second approach, sequential or sometimes called dynamic, enables models to work with time series data, capturing temporal information to construct complete sentences.

A third dimension in the taxonomy is grammar [41], as visual languages possess rich grammatical diversity, much like spoken languages. Sign language grammar

¹Source: www.lifefprint.com/asl101/fingerspelling

includes phonological parameters divided into manual and non-manual markers, with manual markers covering hand shape, movement, location, palm orientation, and body shift. Non-manual markers like body language, eye gaze, and facial expressions add emotional and grammatical context, while classifiers are specialized hand shapes that represent categories or classes of objects, people, or concepts, allowing signers to convey more detailed descriptions beyond individual words. According to this definition, FS is also a special set of manual markers conveying the meaning of concepts without established signs.

Table 1.1: Applying taxonomy on ASL subtasks

Input/Output	Static	Sequential
Static	Static Fingerspelling	-
Sequential	General Sign Prediction	Sequential Translation

As for ASL, static input is only viable for FS and certain grammar markers, as most of the general gestures involve movement, but for sequential input predicting both a single concept or a sentence is possible.

1.5 About This Work

This study addresses the translation of fingerspelled characters and sequences, extending the work conducted in my previous BSc thesis (Section 2.3), in which models for static and sequential fingerspelling were developed and trained [14]. In the present work, a deeper investigation into the representation of gestures as dense vector embeddings is undertaken through the use of Graph Neural Networks, resulting in substantial performance gains over earlier Multi-Layer Perceptron and Convolution-based embedding models. Moreover, a task-optimized fusion of the widely adopted GCN and GAT convolutional architectures is proposed and its effectiveness is evaluated in both controlled experimental conditions, real-world fingerspelling translation and pose approximation scenarios.

The rest of the study is organized as follows:

- **Chapter 2** reviews related work, focusing on foundational approaches in signal processing and translation algorithms essential for translating environmental inputs into model-ready data.
- **Chapter 3** builds the mathematical foundation for Graph Convolutional Networks (GCNs) and Graph Attention Networks (GATs), providing a detailed technical overview of these models, which serve as a basis for later innovations.
- **Chapter 4** presents the proposed methodology, introducing a novel GNN-based embedding model specifically designed to overcome limitations observed with the convolutional embedding layer from the previous study [14].
- **Chapter 5** examines static fingerspelling from a graph-based perspective, validating the concept through isolated gesture recognition.
- **Chapter 6** extends the ideas forward to sequential fingerspelling, evaluating the GNN embedding layer's impact within transformer architectures for continuous translation tasks.
- **Chapter 7** gives a general view about modern pose approximation taxonomy, reviews the advancements in the field and contains an ablation study about the application of neural graph representation.
- **Chapter 8** describes the process of integrating the AI solutions in a hardware-constrained Android environment, alongside extending static fingerspelling models to also translate movement as well.
- Finally, **Chapter 9** concludes the study, summarizing key findings, discussing the superiority of GNN-based models over earlier techniques, and suggesting future research directions in graph-based gesture recognition and sign language translation.

Chapter 2

Related Work

Preliminary research highlights that solutions in the ASL translation field generally include two main components: signal processing and translation algorithms. Signal processing is essential because models cannot directly interpret input from the environment; rather, they require optimal representations of reality from various perspectives. Examples of such representations include segmenting hands in camera images or detecting finger bending in glove-based approaches. Additionally, this step is closely linked to the creation and management of datasets used for model training.

A third component, often overlooked, is the use of supplementary algorithms. In practical applications, these algorithms enhance the reliability and usability of model outputs, especially when deployed in real-world settings.

Figure 2.1: General architecture

2.1 Signal Processing

It is evident from exploratory research that processing the language signal conveyed through the physical medium of hands, is one of the most crucial parts of the whole process. If the representation of the signal is not appropriate, it isn't easy to build well-performing models on it. Signal processing techniques can be divided into three primary categories: traditional image processing methods, hardware-enabled translation systems, and pose estimation-based solutions. Each of these approaches offers distinct advantages and faces unique challenges in accurately capturing and interpreting the complex movements and gestures involved in sign language.

2.1.1 Traditional Image Processing-Based Translation

It is true for such solutions that they transform the images into a higher form of representation like hand segmentation [15], optical flow calculation [17], or artificially generated depth maps [16], however, they don't model the physiology of the hands. This can be vital in situations where not all fingers are visible from a given camera angle, and perhaps the sign cannot be deduced accurately solely from the image information.

2.1.2 Hardware Enabled Translation

In these studies, a suitable hardware device is used to collect the necessary input for the models instead of a camera feed. This in many cases guarantees more sufficient spatial knowledge of the hands. For example, in a recent study, the movement of hands was measured using a ring with IMU sensors [32]. More traditional methods include tracking the exact position of fingers with gloves [1][48][3]. Drawbacks include Hardware cost and inconvenience of use.

2.1.3 Pose Approximation

This third category of processing methods is an innovative image-processing technique aimed at identifying the positions of both visible and concealed hand joints, also referred to as landmarks. This is accomplished through the utilization of deep learning. By exposing the models to numerous examples of manually labeled or hardware-recorded instances, they understand the anatomical intricacies of these joints, enabling them to detect potential joints that may not be directly observable.

This approach boasts 4 important qualities over other methods:

1. Uses the physiological model of the hand without any auxiliary tools.
2. Possibility to extend tracking to posture and facial features.
3. Able to utilize existing video/image format databases.
4. All of the above within real-time constraints.

Two famous baseline algorithms in the field of pose approximation: OpenPose [11] and Mediapipe Holistic [21]. The latter is a composition of 3 separate models: BlazePose [10], MediaPipe Hands [51] and BlazeFace [9]. They both support real-time whole-body tracking from videos and still images as well, but while OpenPose only provides 2D landmarks, Mediapipe also predicts relative depth, referred to as 2.5D [51] by the authors. Intuitively this becomes crucial when gestures involve intertwined fingers, favoring Mediapipe Holistic, but a comparative study [38] with two separate teams in agreement, concluded that: "despite making different predictions, both OpenPose and Holistic performed equally well", and training the model on the combined set of poses yielded the best result. Additionally, efforts are underway to develop models specifically for sign language recognition. For instance, research conducted at the University of Surrey [26] has shown promising results, outperforming MediaPipe across several datasets. This model also enhances 3D performance through a specialized layer that predicts joint angles, enabling the calculation of depth with the propagation of position and rotation from a chosen pivot point using forward kinematics.

2.1.4 Conclusion

There is no clear winner in terms of signal processing methodologies for sign language recognition, as several recent studies, with different algorithms, showed a high degree of accuracy on various datasets [36][18][53], and there are examples where combining different type of processing methods like optical flow, depth maps and "pose skeleton" as a spatial-temporal graph [27] yields the best results.

It must be noted, however, that in recent years pose approximation-based translation has seen a significant bump in popularity and is currently the most popular method to handle gesture translation. Current trends suggest that it will become superior to other methods. A study conducted on the CVPR21 ChaLearn challenge dataset [38] concluded that despite challenges with recognition of overlapping and interacting

hands, "pose estimation features do indeed generalize better to the nature of the challenge, including unseen signers and backgrounds".

2.2 Translation Algorithms

Backed by literature [41], the most common translation algorithms in the field of sign language translation, are encoder-decoder models, out of which Transformers dominate the leaderboards. In this section, I present studies that propose thought-provoking ideas and are also relevant to this research:

1. PoseNet [18] is a Transformer [45] model modified to translate FS sequences into continuous text. Similarly to my previous work (2.3) the full body pose skeleton is provided by MediaPipe Holistic [21], however only the x and y coordinates are utilized during training. For embedding the features, a fully connected layer is applied, scaling them up to the desired dimensions, before using positional embedding. The most intriguing part of the model is a new way of handling the length of the generated sequences: instead of solely relying on the decoder to predict the end of sequence character, the model is capable of computing this information earlier in the encoder layer. Unlike in the general case, there is a 1-1 mapping between fingerspelled characters and the corresponding symbols in the output sequence. Computing this information when the latent space representation is not yet mixed with the decoder input is beneficial according to the author.
2. The idea of imagining the skeletal pose data as a graph is fascinating, as we can apply algorithms designed for processing graphs. The following study [37] works on classifying general sign language poses using this very technique. From the arbitrary long sequences, a spatial-temporal graph is constructed and processed with a modified spatial-temporal graph convolution network [50] (ST-GCN). Each video frame has its isolated graph and the corresponding points on consecutive frames are connected, hence the naming. After unrolling the network a few times, each node in the graph will have a receptive field not only in the spatial but also in the time domain making this method ideal for dynamic movement recognition. In the original study [50] the graph for each frame is connected following the human anatomy, therefore the nodes representing the face and hands are only distantly related in the graph. For signing, however, there's much emphasis on the relative position of distant body parts. Some signs only differ in the position of the face that is touched.

The authors [37] solve this problem by using only a handful of selected key points and constructing their fully connected graph representation.

3. Another approach to this problem is hierarchical spatial-temporal graphs [29]. In this method, graphs are constructed across multiple levels: fine-level graphs represent individual body parts, such as hands and face, while two high-level graphs are constructed with nodes whose features are derived from the bounding boxes around these body parts using optical flow and feature extraction from RGB frames. To process these graphs, specialized GNN layers are applied iteratively. First, features from the fine-level graphs are pooled to construct a new high-level graph, which then undergoes further processing. After several iterations, the graphs are mean-pooled and the latent representation at each time step is concatenated yielding a sequence of dense vectors. The final stage involves a two-step decoding process with LSTM layers: the first LSTM predicts signs at each time step, while a second also LSTM-based encoder-decoder refines these predictions, generating the final output sequence.
4. The following study [36] showcases that graph neural networks can also be applied to images as well. The research presents a dual-stream approach utilizing ResNet-style and graph convolutional layer-based feature extraction. For the latter, the SLIC superpixel [2] algorithm is applied, which clusters nearby pixels into small, coherent regions (superpixels) that group together pixels with similar characteristics, such as color, intensity, or texture. Unlike individual pixels, superpixels capture larger and more meaningful structures within an image, making them useful for simplifying and speeding up higher-level computer vision tasks, like object detection and segmentation. Each superpixel is treated as a node with edges to the neighboring regions. With the dense vector representation, the model performs sign classification.

2.3 Previous Work

Pose approximation techniques were explored in [14] to translate both individual signs and gesture sequences. Several models were built and trained on diverse datasets, and the best-performing models were applied in real-world applications. That study provides the foundation for the current work and is briefly summarized in the following subsections.

2.3.1 Static Fingerspelling

For the task of static fingerspelling, the focus was on handling pose information and building an efficient model. Pose data was captured using the MediaPipe Hands-specific model [51]. Preprocessing involved scaling, centering, and normalizing the x and y coordinates to enhance consistency across samples. Furthermore, I applied data augmentation techniques, including affine transformations, to improve model robustness. A Multi-Layered Perceptron (MLP), optimized with the Hyperband algorithm [33], was trained on the augmented dataset to achieve effective pose classification, with testing conducted on a separate manually recorded dataset.

2.3.2 Sequential Translation

The future of sign language translation lies in sequence-to-sequence algorithms, which have shown great success in traditional language translation by capturing complex relationships within sequences. Unlike general sign prediction, where models interpret isolated frames, sequence-based translation enables a more nuanced contextual understanding.

Implemented models can be split into two families:

1. The first one is an adaptation of the original Transformer architecture [45], with modifications to the embedding layer for handling pose data. (More on that in Section 4.2.) The best architecture includes two encoder layers and four decoder layers, with input sequences padded to a fixed length. The embedding layer incorporates positional encoding based on the original Transformer paper’s approach [45].
2. The second model is based on an encoder-decoder architecture with Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) units (SimpleRNN, LSTM, or GRU) [13]. Here, the encoder’s hidden state vector serves as the latent representation passed to the decoder, which is structured similarly. The same embedding layer as in the Transformer model is applied, though without positional encoding, as the RNN units can naturally encode sequential information.

For training the Kaggle ASL Fingerspelling Competition dataset [6] was used. Since all signers used only one hand, the dominant one was identified with a few other body and facial key points. After normalization, the landmarks were concatenated to form the final input. The results were consistent with the findings reported in the literature [41], namely the Transformer models came out superior.

Figure 2.2: (a) Transformer model (b) Encoder–decoder with recurrent units

Despite performing well, in this follow-up research, I explore a more advanced approach using graph neural networks (GNNs) to generate pose embeddings. This newer approach has demonstrated superior performance in both hand pose classification and continuous fingerspelling recognition, surpassing the earlier models.

Chapter 3

Graph Neural Networks

Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) are deep learning models designed to work with graph-structured data, where relationships between entities are as essential as the entities themselves. In traditional machine learning, data is often represented in grids or sequences, like images or text. However, graphs provide a way to model complex relationships, with nodes (vertices) representing entities and edges representing connections between them. GNNs extend the power of neural networks to this relational data by learning from both the features of nodes and the graph structure.

The concept of representing pose information as a graph, where nodes denote key points and edges represent anatomical connections, has intrigued me for a long time. Because GNNs excel at capturing relationships in structured data, they offer a promising approach for modeling complex spatial relationships. This fascination led me to develop a novel GNN-based embedding layer aimed at enhancing sign language translation accuracy. In this chapter, I provide a detailed technical overview of this approach, forging a strong foundation for later sections.

3.1 Intuition

GNN is a general umbrella term for architectures specifically designed to exploit the relational nature of datasets. One of the most common architectures is Graph Convolutional Networks (GCNs), which expand the idea of regular CNN layers for graphs. In CNNs, a filter of arbitrary size slides across an image, calculating the sum of element-wise products between filter values and corresponding pixel values. With automatic differentiation and backpropagation, CNNs learn to extract meaningful features from images based on a specified objective function. Extending this

principle to graphs, an image can be conceptualized as a graph structure, with each pixel representing a node and edges linking adjacent pixels. Nodes have different values (features) associated with them, like in the case of images the RGB values. GNNs enable localized feature extraction from graph-structured data by generalizing this approach, facilitating efficient learning of complex relationships within arbitrary graphs.

Figure 3.1: Illustration of 2D convolution and graph convolution [49]

Properties of the ideal graph convolution layer include:

1. **Learnable parameters:** Parameters that can be optimized during training to capture meaningful features.
2. **Computational and storage efficiency:** The layer should be efficient enough to support iterative applications within deep networks.
3. **Localization:** Focused processing of nearby nodes, as these typically contain the most relevant information.
4. **Flexible node weighting:** Different nodes should be weighted based on their significance in the context of the graph.

Applying such a layer will result in a new graph with a different set of node features and with deep learning the models can learn to create a meaningful representation for each node. From here the most common operation is to predict some property from these "latent" feature vectors on the node level. Still, for this study, it is much more useful to aggregate the node-level data to gather information on the whole graph, from which for example the classification of the gestures can happen.

3.2 Formalizing The Problem

A graph can be formally represented as $G = (V, E)$, where V is the set of nodes (or vertices) and $E \subseteq V \times V$ is the set of edges.

In a graph with N nodes, the features are represented by a matrix $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times F}$, where F denotes the number of features per node. Each row vector, denoted as \vec{x}_i , corresponds to the features of the i -th node in \mathbf{X} . It is important to note that all vectors in this study are treated as row vectors, and edge-level attributes are excluded from consideration.

The adjacency matrix $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$, where each entry \mathbf{A}_{ij} indicates the presence (or weight) of an edge between nodes i and j . For our purposes (undirected, unweighted graph):

$$\mathbf{A}_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } i \leftrightarrow j \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3.1)$$

Given a graph G with adjacency matrix \mathbf{A} and node features \mathbf{X} , the objective of GNNs is to learn a function $f : \mathbb{R}^{N \times F} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{N \times O}$, where O is the dimension of the output feature space. The iterative application of f across layers can be expressed as:

$$\mathbf{H}^{(i+1)} = f^{(i)}(\mathbf{H}^{(i)}, \mathbf{A}) \quad (3.2)$$

The initial node features are represented by $\mathbf{H}^{(0)} = \mathbf{X}$, with $f^{(i)}$ as the update function applied at layer i . This iterative formula allows the progressive extension of each node’s “receptive field”, which is the set of nodes from which it gathers information. With each new layer, nodes gain a broader view, integrating insights from increasingly distant neighbors. This gradual expansion enables the model to learn representations that capture both local and global patterns, depending on the number of layers.

Note that a simple neural network applied directly to the adjacency and feature matrices is not suitable for graph data due to two key limitations:

1. **Varying Graph Sizes:** Different graphs have different numbers of nodes, resulting in adjacency and feature matrices of varying shapes. Standard neural networks require fixed-size inputs, making them ill-suited for graphs of arbitrary size.
2. **Lack of Node Permutation Invariance:** A neural network’s output depends on the order of nodes in the input matrices, but the graph structure should remain unchanged regardless of node ordering. Simple neural networks cannot handle this permutation invariance, resulting in different outputs for the same graph with varied node arrangements.

3.3 Message Passing Networks

To exploit localization, which is one of the most important criteria in the requirements presented in Section 3.1, we focus on how a node i communicates with its immediate neighbors. During the so-called "message passing" process, each node i gathers information from its neighbors $j \in \mathcal{N}(i)$ through a series of steps:

1. **Message Generation:** Each neighboring node j computes a message m_{ij} intended for node i . This message can be derived from its feature vector \vec{x}_j , the feature vector of node i , and, in certain specialized scenarios, edge features. The formula for message generation can be expressed as:

$$\vec{m}_{ij} = \phi(\vec{x}_i, \vec{x}_j) \quad (3.3)$$

where ϕ represents a learnable function, which could be a linear transformation, a multi-layer perceptron (MLP), or even a more complex operation depending on the specific architecture.

2. **Aggregation:** After generating messages from all neighboring nodes, node i aggregates these incoming messages. The aggregation function AGG combines the messages in a way that maintains permutation invariance.

$$\vec{m}_i = \text{AGG}_{j \in \mathcal{N}(i)}(\vec{m}_{ij}) \quad (3.4)$$

3. **Update:** Finally, node i updates its feature vector by incorporating the aggregated message. This step typically involves a learnable function that merges the aggregated message with the node’s current feature vector, represented as:

$$\vec{h}_i = g(\vec{m}_i, \vec{x}_i) \quad (3.5)$$

where g is another learnable function, which could vary in form, ranging from a simple linear transformation to a more intricate neural network structure and \vec{h}_i is the updated feature vector, or i -th row of $\mathbf{H}^{(i)}$ from Equation 3.2.

Through this localized message-passing process, each node effectively captures and integrates the features of its local neighborhood. This mechanism facilitates the learning of representations that are sensitive to the graph’s structure, enabling the model to generalize effectively across various graph topologies.

However, in its general form, this approach is often limited to smaller graphs and complex problems involving edge features, as certain aspects can frequently be simplified to enhance computational efficiency while still achieving comparable performance. By strategically reducing complexity, we can leverage the strengths of message passing in larger and more intricate graph structures.

3.4 Graph Convolution Networks

A common approach for transforming the general message-passing process presented in Section 3.3 is to compute the messages by applying linear transformations to both the sender node’s feature vectors and also to the receiving node’s as well. It is also common practice to introduce non-linearity to the system:

$$\vec{h}_i = \sigma \left(\text{AGG}_{j \in \mathcal{N}(i)} (\vec{x}_j \mathbf{W}) + \vec{x}_i \mathbf{W}' \right) \quad (3.6)$$

where:

- \mathbf{W} and \mathbf{W}' are learned weight matrices, which are often equal, representing linear transformations,
- σ is an activation function that introduces non-linearity to the model.

If the same linear transformation is applied to both \vec{x}_i and \vec{x}_j ($\mathbf{W} = \mathbf{W}'$), while taking the average of transformed node features to aggregate them, we arrive at the concept of graph convolution layers:

$$\vec{h}_i = \sigma \left(\frac{1}{|\hat{\mathcal{N}}(i)|} \sum_{j \in \hat{\mathcal{N}}(i)} \vec{x}_j \mathbf{W} \right) \quad (3.7)$$

where $\hat{\mathcal{N}}(i)$ represents the neighborhood of the i th node, with an added self loop.

Expressing this in matrix form allows us to rewrite the graph update rule from Equation 3.2 as:

$$\mathbf{H}^{(i+1)} = \sigma \left(\hat{\mathbf{D}}^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{A}} \mathbf{H}^{(i)} \mathbf{W}^{(i)} \right) \quad (3.8)$$

where:

- $\hat{\mathbf{A}} = \mathbf{A} + \mathbf{I}$ is the adjacency matrix with added self-loops, with \mathbf{I} being the identity matrix.
- $\hat{\mathbf{D}}$ is the degree matrix of $\hat{\mathbf{A}}$, defined as: $\hat{\mathbf{D}}_{ii} = \sum_j \hat{A}_{ij}$ which sums the elements of the i -th row of $\hat{\mathbf{A}}$ to determine the degree of node i .
- Note, that the Transposition of $\mathbf{W}^{(i)}$ is omitted, because it is learned

An interesting additional thing that Thomas N. Kipf, Max Welling did in the original paper [31] is to use "symmetric normalization". Instead of calculating the mean they normalized the adjacency matrix by the inverse square root of the degree matrix:

$$\mathbf{H}^{(i+1)} = \sigma \left(\hat{\mathbf{D}}^{-\frac{1}{2}} \hat{\mathbf{A}} \hat{\mathbf{D}}^{-\frac{1}{2}} \mathbf{H}^{(i)} \mathbf{W}^{(i)} \right) \quad (3.9)$$

$$\mathbf{h}_i = \sigma \left(\sum_{j \in \hat{\mathcal{N}}(i)} \frac{1}{\sqrt{|\hat{\mathcal{N}}(i)| |\hat{\mathcal{N}}(j)|}} \vec{x}_j \mathbf{W} \right) \quad (3.10)$$

The effect of this approach is further illustrated in Equation 3.10. Intuitively this technique ensures that the message from each neighbor is scaled by the number of connections it has so that nodes with a high connectivity are not overrepresented. This GCNConv layer is one of the most popular approaches when it comes to GNNs.

3.5 Graph Attention Networks

Graph Attention Networks [46] or GAT for short, boast the ability to learn which nodes are important when performing message passing. This is especially appealing in terms of treating the hands as graphs, from which the model can learn anatomical details based on connected joints.

The main difference between GCNConv and Graph Attention Network (GAT) lies in how they aggregate information from neighboring nodes in a graph. GAT introduces an attention mechanism that allows the model to assign different importance, or “attention scores,” to different neighbors during the aggregation. Each neighbor’s contribution is weighed dynamically based on learned attention coefficients, enabling GAT to focus more on influential nodes and less on irrelevant ones. While GCNConv is simpler and computationally efficient, GAT provides more flexibility by learning to emphasize specific neighbors, which can improve performance in cases where certain connections are more informative than others. So compared to GCNConv, it essentially changes how the latent node features are calculated in Equation 3.7 to:

$$\mathbf{h}_i = \sigma \left(\sum_{j \in \hat{\mathcal{N}}(i)} \alpha_{ij} \vec{x}_j \mathbf{W} \right) \quad (3.11)$$

$$\alpha_{ij} = \frac{\exp \left(\text{LeakyReLU} \left(\vec{a}^T \left[\vec{h}_i \mathbf{W} \parallel \vec{h}_j \mathbf{W} \right] \right) \right)}{\sum_{k \in \hat{\mathcal{N}}(i)} \exp \left(\text{LeakyReLU} \left(\vec{a}^T \left[\vec{h}_i \mathbf{W} \parallel \vec{h}_k \mathbf{W} \right] \right) \right)} \quad (3.12)$$

where:

- \parallel denotes concatenation,
- $\vec{a} \in \mathbb{R}^{2O}$ represents the learnable parameters for a shared attention mechanism. (O is the output feature dimension of the layer.)

By having access to the transformed features of the two nodes, it can learn relevance based on their “content”. Note that without applying the special *softmax* at the end each node could “attend” to any other, throwing away the structure of the graph.

Figure 3.2: Illustration of GAT conv layer from the original study [46]: **Left:** The attention mechanism $a(\vec{h}_i \mathbf{W}, \vec{h}_j \mathbf{W})$, parametrized by a weight vector $\vec{a} \in \mathbb{R}^{2O}$, applying a LeakyReLU activation and finally a special softmax to preserve structure. **Right:** An illustration of multi-head attention (with 3 heads) on node 1 and its neighborhood. Different arrow styles and colors denote independent attention computations. The aggregated features from each head are concatenated or averaged to obtain \vec{h}'_1 .

3.6 Mini-Batching for Graph Data

Implementing graph-level data batching presented a technical challenge. Unlike vectors, graphs often vary in size, meaning their adjacency matrices and node feature vectors cannot be batched directly. PyTorch Geometric [19], a PyTorch extension for working with graphs and Graph Neural Networks (GNNs), addresses this issue with a specialized mini-batching technique, which involves merging the graphs in the following three steps:

1. **Concatenate Node Feature Vectors:** Each graph’s node feature vectors (e.g., \mathbf{X}_i in Equation 3.13) are concatenated, forming a unified feature representation for the batch.
2. **Track Graph Membership:** An index array is maintained to indicate which graph each feature vector belongs to, preserving the structure and association of features within each graph.

3. **Diagonal Concatenation of Adjacency Matrices:** The adjacency matrices (e.g., \mathbf{A}_i in Equation 3.13) for each graph are combined along the diagonal to form a single, large sparse matrix, effectively creating a merged graph with isolated subgraphs. Using a sparse matrix reduces storage overhead.

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A}_1 & & \\ & \ddots & \\ & & \mathbf{A}_n \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{X} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{X}_1 \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{X}_n \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.13)$$

With this approach, the Graph Neural Network (GNN) layers can compute updates validly, as node updates in the used layers rely on information solely from each node and its immediate neighbors.

3.7 Task Optimized Graph Convolution

Graphs can take many forms; their structure is part of the data and therefore subject to change. In this study, however, the anatomy of the hands stays fixed throughout the training. Referring back to Equation 3.9, the normalized adjacency matrix ($\hat{\mathbf{D}}^{-\frac{1}{2}} \hat{\mathbf{A}} \hat{\mathbf{D}}^{-\frac{1}{2}}$) is essentially constant. This presents a unique opportunity to optimize the batching process for GCN Convolution, as there is no need to handle a batch of graphs with a block diagonal compound matrix as seen in Equation 3.13. Taking it one step further, GCN equations can be rewritten with a trainable parameter matrix ($\mathbf{W}_1^{(i)}$) instead of the constant adjacency matrix:

$$\mathbf{H}^{(i+1)} = \sigma \left(\mathbf{W}_1^{(i)} \mathbf{H}^{(i)} \mathbf{W}_2^{(i)} \right) \quad (3.14)$$

Notes:

1. In Pytorch Geometric GCN Conv implementation, multiplication with $\mathbf{W}_2^{(i)}$ is implemented as a full linear transformation with bias addition included. Results in later chapters were produced by models that also include this extra operation.
2. The parameter can be initialized randomly or for specific graphs with adjacency matrix (\mathbf{A}), and the familiar normalization formula:

$$\mathbf{W}_1^{(0)} = \hat{\mathbf{D}}^{-\frac{1}{2}} \hat{\mathbf{A}} \hat{\mathbf{D}}^{-\frac{1}{2}} \quad (3.15)$$

Intuitively, this means that this modified GCN Conv layer learns the parameters of an optimal weighted directional graph. This is similar to the concept of GAT Conv layers, but also different in the sense that weights (attention scores) are computed "dynamically", based on the feature vectors of the nodes, but here they only depend on the nodes themselves. The model, in theory, can learn which connections are important for the given deep learning task, which should additionally help to make the models more explainable.

3.8 Implementation Details

Two distinct implementation strategies were employed. First, standard GNN architectures were constructed using the PyTorch Geometric library to establish a baseline. The Pytorch Module is capable of instantiating either GCN or GAT as presented in Listing 3.1, utilizes standard message-passing primitives, respectively GCNConv and GATConv.

```

1 from torch_geometric.nn import GCNConv, GATConv, global_mean_pool
2
3 class StandardGNN(nn.Module):
4     def __init__(self, num_layers: int, hidden_dim: int,
5                 num_classes: int, layer_type: Literal["gcn", "gat"]):
6         super().__init__()
7
8         self.convs = nn.ModuleList()
9
10        LayerClass = GATConv if layer_type == "gat" else GCNConv
11
12        # Input Layer
13        self.convs.append(LayerClass(dataset.num_features, hidden_dim))
14
15        # Hidden Layers
16        for _ in range(num_layers - 1):
17            self.convs.append(LayerClass(hidden_dim, hidden_dim))
18
19        self.classifier = nn.Linear(hidden_dim, num_classes)
20
21    def forward(self, x, edge_index, batch):
22        # 1. Message Passing Phase
23        for conv in self.convs:
24            x = conv(x, edge_index)
25            x = F.relu(x)
26
27        # 2. Readout Phase (Global Pooling)
28        x = global_mean_pool(x, batch)
29
30        # 3. Classification Phase
31        return self.classifier(x)

```

Listing 3.1: Generalized PyTorch Geometric GNN implementation

Using the disjoint union strategy from Equation 3.13, this implementation natively supports diverse topologies, such as social networks and molecular structures, without sacrificing flexibility to implement various algorithms.

3.8.1 Custom Graph Convolution

In the context of hand pose classification, the graph topology is constant. The disjoint union strategy is therefore unnecessary. To optimize for this, the theoretical framework was realized through a custom module, named `MobileGNNConv` (Listing 3.2).

```

1 class MobileGNNConv(nn.Module):
2     def __init__(self, input_dim: int, output_dim: int,
3                 random_init: bool = False):
4         super().__init__()
5         self.lin = nn.Linear(input_dim, output_dim, bias=True)
6
7         # Adjacency Initialization
8         if random_init:
9             # Stochastic initialization for latent structure discovery
10            self.A_norm = nn.Parameter(
11                torch.empty(NUM_NODES, NUM_NODES),
12                requires_grad=False
13            )
14            nn.init.kaiming_uniform_(self.A_norm, a=math.sqrt(5))
15        else:
16            A = torch.zeros((NUM_NODES, NUM_NODES))
17            # Anatomical prior-based initialization, defined elsewhere
18            for x, y in anatomical_connections:
19                A[x, y] = 1
20
21            # GCN Normalization:  $D^{-1/2} * (A + I) * D^{-1/2}$ 
22            A_hat = A + torch.eye(A.size(0))
23            D = torch.diag(A_hat.sum(dim=1))
24            D_inv_sqrt = torch.linalg.inv(torch.sqrt(D))
25            A_norm = D_inv_sqrt @ A_hat @ D_inv_sqrt
26
27            # Registered as a parameter to allow for optional gradient updates
28            self.A_norm = nn.Parameter(A_norm, requires_grad=False)
29
30        def set_adjacency(self, *, trainable: bool):
31            """Toggles the gradient requirement for the structure matrix."""
32            self.A_norm.requires_grad = trainable
33
34        def forward(self, X: torch.Tensor):
35            # Dense matrix multiplication:  $(A_{norm} * X) * W^T + b$ 
36            return F.relu(self.lin(self.A_norm @ X))

```

Listing 3.2: PyTorch implementation of the task-optimized graph convolution layer

This implementation diverges from the standard library approach by enforcing fixed graph topology. Data is processed as dense tensors of shape $(BatchSize \times N_{hand} \times F)$, allowing the adjacency matrix to be treated as a shared, dense parameter broadcasted across the batch dimension.

The initialization process (`__init__`) constructs the structural matrix $\mathbf{W}_1^{(i)}$. When derived from anatomical constraints, the symmetric normalization ($\hat{\mathbf{D}}^{-\frac{1}{2}}\hat{\mathbf{A}}\hat{\mathbf{D}}^{-\frac{1}{2}}$) is pre-computed and cached as a model parameter. This eliminates the computational cost of dynamic normalization per pass.

Furthermore, a distinct feature of this implementation is the `set_adjacency` method. By modifying the gradient requirement of the adjacency parameter, the topological structure can be transitioned from a static constant to a learnable variable. This allows the backpropagation algorithm to directly optimize the edge weights, a feature not easily replicated with the sparse disjoint union approach used by standard GCN implementations.

Further details about the experimental setup and evaluation results are available in Chapter 5.

Chapter 4

Proposed Methodology

Building upon the promising results of the former study [14], this chapter explores potential performance improvements. Recent literature [41] highlights the effectiveness of transformer-based architectures with pose approximation for sign language translation, raising motivation to retain this approach while exploring graph-based representations of hand motion. Specifically, this chapter examines the limitations of the previously used convolution-based embedding layer and introduces a new GNN architecture designed to address these issues. Additionally, the technological challenges involved in developing and optimizing the proposed approach are discussed.

4.1 Embedding Layers for Sign Translation

Creating dense vector embeddings is a standard mechanism in deep learning for capturing semantic structure in compact representations, enabling efficient learning and generalization. In neural machine translation (NMT), discrete tokens are mapped to embedding vectors via an index-based lookup, formalized as $f_{trad} : \mathbb{Z}^t \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{t \times d}$, where t denotes sequence length and d the embedding dimension. In contrast, pose estimation data requires embedding continuous feature vectors rather than indices, resulting in a mapping $f : \mathbb{R}^{t \times 3n} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{t \times d}$, where each time step encodes the x, y, z coordinates of n selected key points. Consequently, the embedding function must remain computationally efficient while preserving the semantic and spatial structure of the input. In transformer-based NMT models, positional encoding [45] is employed to retain temporal ordering information critical for sequence modeling.

4.2 Convolutional Pose Embedding

The applied solution in the successor study was a 1D Convolution-based embedding layer. This type of architecture is suitable for encoding temporal information in the embedding vectors. The input ($X \in \mathbb{R}^{t \times 3n}$) was treated as having $3n$ features at each time step t . Let $W \in \mathbb{R}^{k \times 3n \times h}$ represent a convolutional kernel with width k , which applies across the time dimension, and h is the number of filters or output channels. The sequence was padded evenly to the left and right to preserve the temporal dimension, with $k - 1$ padding tokens. The output $Y \in \mathbb{R}^{t \times h}$ will thus have the same temporal dimension t but h channels.

$$Y(x, c) = \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} \sum_{j=1}^{3n} W(i, j, c) \cdot \hat{X}(x + i - p_{left}, j) \quad (4.1)$$

where:

1. $x \in [0, t - 1]$ indexes the time step, and $c \in [1, h]$ indexes the output channels,
2. \hat{X} refers to the padded input,
3. $p_{left} = \lfloor \frac{k-1}{2} \rfloor$, $p_{right} = \lceil \frac{k-1}{2} \rceil$ representing the left and right padding.

4.2.1 Implementation

The implementation of the convolutional embedding relies on the standard 1D convolution operation. However, a specific discrepancy exists between the standard data format of sequence modeling and the input requirements of convolutional layers in the PyTorch framework.

Sequence data is typically structured as tensors of shape (B, T, F) , where B is the batch size, T is the sequence length, and F denotes the number of features. Conversely, the `nn.Conv1d` module requires the channel dimension to be the second dimension, anticipating an input of shape (B, F, T) . To reconcile this, a permutation operation is employed within the forward pass. As shown in Listing 4.1, the input tensor is permuted prior to the convolutional block and reverted immediately after.

Furthermore, to ensure the preservation of the temporal dimension as discussed in Section 4.2, the `padding='same'` argument is utilized. This relieves the architecture of manual padding calculations, ensuring that the output sequence length remains identical to the input length T , regardless of the kernel size selected.

```

1 class LandmarkEmbedding(nn.Module):
2     def __init__(self, d_model, num_features, num_conv_layers, filter_size):
3         super().__init__()
4
5         # Initial projection layer
6         first_conv = nn.Conv1d(in_channels=num_features,
7                                out_channels=d_model,
8                                kernel_size=filter_size,
9                                padding='same')
10
11        # Stacking subsequent layers
12        rest_of_convs = [
13            nn.Conv1d(in_channels=d_model,
14                     out_channels=d_model,
15                     kernel_size=filter_size,
16                     padding='same')
17            for _ in range(num_conv_layers-1)
18        ]
19
20        self.conv_block = nn.Sequential(first_conv, *rest_of_convs)
21
22    def forward(self, x):
23        # Input x shape: (batch_size, seq_len, num_features)
24
25        # Trick: Permute to (batch, features, seq_len) for Conv1d
26        x = x.permute(0, 2, 1)
27
28        x = self.conv_block(x)
29
30        # Revert to (batch, seq_len, d_model) for Transformer
31        x = x.permute(0, 2, 1)
32        return x

```

Listing 4.1: Implementation of the 1D convolutional landmark embedding

4.2.2 Criticism and Potential Improvements

There are a few interesting problems with this setup:

1. **Semantic mismatch with traditional positional encoding:** In transformer-based NMT, positional encoding provides each token with a unique representation based on its position in the sequence, helping the model interpret the order of information. With convolution, however, a window of k input time steps influences the embedding at each time step. This means that applying positional information isn't necessarily correct semantically.
2. **Handling padding:** In cases where sequences differ in length, padding shorter ones adds more than just a single padding token per time step; it introduces a vector of size $3n$ for each padded element. This can obscure the

true end of the sequence, making it harder for the model to distinguish meaningful content due to the influence of the padding within the kernel length. Moreover, applying masking in the encoder isn't straightforward, as there isn't a direct one-to-one correspondence between feature values and the embedding vectors, complicating the masking process.

3. **Missing Points:** When the hands are cut off by the video frame, or in case of detection failure, there are potentially missing values for certain joints. Handling this with rigid input sizes, required by convolutional layers, leaves only to "pad" those missing values. Note that this type of intra-frame padding is different from padding sequences to a fixed length in the time domain discussed in the previous point. Graphs, on the other hand, allow for a less rigid structure with removed nodes as a potential replacement for missing joint coordinates. However, this also comes with a trade-off, because several optimization strategies could rely on having uniform graphs, which is especially prominent in the case of batching graph data for training discussed in Section 4.3.2. Nevertheless, the hypothesis that handling "damaged" data with graphs leads to better performance is worth exploring in the future.

4.3 Graph Neural Network-Based Embedding

With this new component, the goal is to fix the semantic problems with the convolution-based embedding layer, while also utilizing the concealed information in the structure of the data. While the ultimate challenge is to enhance sequential translation, starting in a bottom-up style, working with data from a single time frame first, presents a unique opportunity to validate and optimize the idea before over-investing in immature solutions. Preliminary literature [29] [37] highlights several ways of dealing with distant nodes in the whole skeleton graph, but ultimately only the dominant hands of the signers were used, similarly to the previous research. [14]. This is not a restriction in the case of ASL fingerspelling, as conveyed meaning is deducible by solely looking at a single hand.

4.3.1 Case of Isolated Data Point

First, a graph is constructed using the 21 MediaPipe key points of the dominant hand with 3 features (x,y,z) for each node and connecting them anatomically with the additional connections of the neighboring knuckles, as they can't move independently

from each other. Thanks to the flexibility of PyTorch Geometric [19], the structure of the graph could later be modified for experimenting.

Figure 4.1: Anatomy of hand joints [20]

GNN layers described in Chapter 3 were applied. These layers essentially update the "state" of the graph by iteratively updating the feature vectors of each node. Multiple layers were stacked to experiment with different receptive field sizes. As for the GATConv layers, there is an option to increase the number of attention heads, which has the effect of running the layer with different attention weights. This can be essential in certain scenarios due to the shared nature of these parameters. There are two options for handling the additional data that comes with the extra heads: either compute their mean or concatenate them and apply an optional downscale transformation to retain the original dimensions as seen in the multi-head attention implementation of the Attention is All You Need paper [45]. As a final step, average pooling was used to get the dense vector representation of the whole graph. For classifying the gestures, any neural network can be operated on this latent space vector.

4.3.2 Sequential Data Points

The input for such a task is not treated as a spatial-temporal graph as in [50], because one of the main goals with this embedding layer was to treat individual data points separately so that a one-to-one match exists between the embedding and captured pose frame. The key to keeping this property is to process each time step separately with the architecture presented in Section 4.3.1. The implementation of the GNN-based embedding, however, presents a higher degree of complexity, primarily due to the handling of mini-batches in graph learning. Unlike standard tensors, graphs in a

mini-batch are typically processed as a single disjoint union of subgraphs containing $B \times T$ isolated graph instances. This enables the adjacency matrix (edge index) to be processed in a block-diagonal format, thereby maximizing GPU throughput. Compounding this complexity, each entry in the sequential dataset consists of a set of graphs, meaning that sequence length also impacts the "mini-batch" size. For instance, representing each entry with 21 key points as nodes produces an adjacency matrix of size $441T^2b^2$, where T is the sequence length and b is the batch size. This matrix must be constructed for each batch, making caching valuable. Consequently, the Graph Embedding layer must be aware of the batch size, introducing a minor dependency that slightly complicates the architecture. In the end, keeping the batch size at 32 and utilizing a GPU, the resource budget was manageable.

To navigate these architectural constraints and ensure computational efficiency, the implementation presented in Listing 4.2 employs three specific implementation strategies:

1. **Data Flattening:** The input tensor of shape (B, T, F) is reshaped (flattened) into $(B \times T, F)$ at the beginning of the forward pass. The temporal dimension is effectively collapsed into the batch dimension, as the GNN treats every time step as an independent graph sample.
2. **Static Graph Caching:** A significant optimization is observed in the initialization phase. Since the topological structure of the hand (the connections between joints) remains constant across all time steps and all samples, the edge index does not need to be recomputed for every forward pass; hence, the `single_graph_edge_index` is constructed once. Furthermore, a "dummy" mini-batch is generated during initialization to pre-calculate the batched edge indices and batch assignment vectors. These are registered as buffers (`self.register_buffer`), allowing them to be moved to the GPU automatically with the model, thereby avoiding the significant overhead of creating and transferring Data objects to the GPU during the training loop.
3. **Global Pooling and Restoration:** Following the node-level updates via GCN or GAT layers, the node features must be aggregated to form a graph-level embedding. This is achieved via `global_mean_pool`, which utilizes the pre-calculated `batch_info` vector to average node features belonging to the same graph instance. Finally, the tensor is reshaped back to (B, T, d_{model}) to restore the sequence structure required for subsequent temporal processing steps.

```

1 class GraphEmbedding(nn.Module):
2     def __init__(self, num_nodes, num_features, d_model,
3                 hidden_dim, seq_len, batch_size, layer_type, num_layers):
4         super().__init__()
5
6         # ... [Layer initialization omitted for brevity] ...
7
8         # Optimization: Precompute connections once
9         connections = [ (0,1), (0,5), (0,17), (1,2), ... ] # truncated
10        edges = []
11        for a, b in connections:
12            edges.append([a, b])
13            edges.append([b, a])
14        single_edge_index = torch.tensor(edges, dtype=torch.long).t().contiguous()
15
16        # Trick: Create a static mini-batch to cache edge_index and batch vector
17        # This assumes fixed batch_size and seq_len during training.
18        dummy_x = torch.zeros(num_nodes, num_features)
19        data_list = [
20            Data(x=dummy_x, edge_index=single_edge_index)
21            for _ in range(batch_size * seq_len)
22        ]
23        mini_batch = Batch.from_data_list(data_list)
24
25        # Register buffers to save GPU transfer/creation time in forward pass
26        self.register_buffer('edge_index', mini_batch.edge_index)
27        self.register_buffer('batch_info', mini_batch.batch)
28
29    def forward(self, x):
30        # x shape: (batch_size, seq_len, num_features)
31
32        # Flatten batch and time dimensions for Graph processing
33        x = x.reshape(-1, self.num_features_per_node)
34
35        # GNN Layers (using cached edge_index)
36        for layer in self.graph_conv:
37            x = layer(x, self.edge_index)
38
39        # Aggregate node features -> Graph Embedding
40        x = global_mean_pool(x, self.batch_info)
41
42        # Reshape back to sequence format
43        x = x.reshape(self.batch_size, self.seq_len, self.d_model)
44        return x

```

Listing 4.2: Implementation of the graph embedding with static edge caching

A potential future solution to the sub-optimality of sequential graph data batching is the optimized GNN layer from Section 3.7. This type of layer could significantly reduce the resource intensity of the embedding layer while keeping similar performance.

Chapter 5

Static Fingerspelling

Translating American Sign Language fingerspelling (ASL FS) from static images may initially seem unconventional, as signs often require motion to be fully understood. This limitation means the model will likely struggle with specific gestures that depend on movement, but using static images serves as a foundational step toward more complex translation tasks. Beyond sign language translation, recognizing isolated gestures has applications in gesture-based human-computer interaction, where detecting certain signs can indicate intent and changes in joint positions can drive spatial actions like dragging. Nonetheless, ASL FS can be used to validate the idea of interpreting pose approximation data as a graph for neural processing and as a stepping stone for sequential FS.

5.1 Dataset

In this study, the same dataset is used as in the previous research [14]. Namely, the Sign Language MNIST [28], the University of Exeter ASL [39], and a self-recorded set of FS gestures. Due to low image quality, in the case of the first two, enhancement techniques were applied to improve conversion rates with MediaPipe Hands [51]. Super-resolution algorithms had a limited impact, but the ECCV16 colorization model [52] was crucial for the MNIST dataset, as the pose approximation algorithm required RGB images. This approach enabled successful pose extraction for approximately 31% of the Sign Language MNIST and 39% of the University of Exeter ASL datasets.

For preprocessing, I explored a new approach aimed at addressing the issue where variations in camera focal lengths and signer distances cause hand skeletons to ap-

pear significantly different. This approach (Figure 5.1) minimizes the effect of these factors. The steps are as follows:

- Similarly to the previous study [14] only the x,y components are processed as z only indicates relative depth. Ultimately, the three axes are stacked together again.
- First, the points are centered by shifting the coordinates so that their mean aligns with the origin, allowing for symmetric scaling around the center.
- Then, the maximum distance of any point from the origin is determined separately for both axes. This enables the calculation of independent scaling factors for each axis, effectively resizing the points to fit within a standard range along both directions.

Figure 5.1: Visualization of preprocessing steps

5.2 Experimental Setup

To compare the performance and suitability of various GNN architectures for pose classification, several experiments were conducted with a standard 80/10/10 train-validation-test split. Initially, each GNN model was trained for 30 epochs, with a batch size of 256.

Figure 5.2: Block diagram of used model architectures

Performance was evaluated across the following configurations, with the reference implementation explained in Listing 3.1.

- **GNN Layer Type:** Two GNN architectures were examined, specifically GCN [31] and GAT [46]. For GAT, four attention heads were employed in each layer to stabilize the mechanism throughout the experiment.
- **Model Layers:** Different layer depths were tested, with models configured at 1, 2, and 3 layers. This setup allowed analysis of the relationship between receptive field expansion and performance.
- **Hidden Size Variations:** The hidden layer output dimensions were varied at three levels, small (32), medium (64), and large (128), to observe the effect of hidden dimensions on model performance.

After finding the best GCN and GAT-based models, their performance is compared with the MLP model from the previous study in a longer training session.

5.3 Results

First, the performance of GCN and GAT models was evaluated based on the accuracy achieved across different configurations. As shown in Table 5.2, both GNN architectures demonstrated improved accuracy with increased model depth and hidden layer size. Notably, GAT models consistently outperformed GCN models across

all configurations, achieving the highest test accuracy of 96.58% with three layers and a "large hidden size". This trend suggests that the attention mechanism in GAT provides a significant advantage in capturing complex relationships within the pose classification task.

Table 5.1: Test accuracies and number of parameters

Model	Layers	Accuracy (%)			Parameters		
		Small	Medium	Large	Small	Medium	Large
GCN	1	60.00%	66.18%	70.49%	855	1687	3351
	2	81.07%	84.07%	86.89%	1911	5847	19863
	3	83.90%	88.37%	90.53%	2967	10007	36375
GAT	1	82.21%	89.16%	91.53%	1975	5975	20119
	2	92.07%	94.76%	95.90%	4151	14423	53399
	3	92.55%	95.11%	96.58%	6327	22871	86679

Comparing the best models in a longer training session, with 100 epochs, the 3-layer Large GAT increased the performance by a significant margin compared to the Multi-Layer Perceptron from the previous study, while the 3-layer Large GCN performed roughly midway between the two. Figure 5.3 shows the best accuracies compared to the 10-Fold Cross Validation metrics, which also reveals that Graph-based models were less sensitive to changes in the dataset. Moreover, Figure 5.5 reveals a more detailed representation of the training process.

Figure 5.3: Best model configuration performance comparison after 100 epochs

Figure 5.4: Runtime comparison of GNN architectures

The computational efficiency of the embedding layer configurations was also compared. The result is a heatmap (5.4), showing the mean runtime of each layer over 700 iterations with a batch size of 256. The experiments were conducted on an Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU @ 2.00GHz CPU with 32 GBs of DDR4 RAM, with a Tesla P100-PCIE-16GB GPU. The analysis highlights an engineering trade-off between performance and runtime when comparing GCN and GAT layer types. Notably, increasing the hidden layer dimensions incurs lower costs than adding additional layers, regardless of the hardware used. The impact of transitioning from a small to medium or large hidden dimension size is negligible on the GPU; this is because it primarily increases the size of the matrices being multiplied, which GPUs excel at parallelizing. When considering real-time performance, only the CPU implementation of the three-layer Large GAT scores below 60 fps, indicating that computational efficiency is not a significant concern.

Figure 5.5: Validation accuracy comparison

5.4 Testing Hypotheses

Beyond identifying the best-performing model, several hypotheses were examined to better understand the capabilities and limitations of GNN models for pose classification:

1. **Effect of Preprocessing on Model Type:** tested by assessing the effect of preprocessing on top-performing models. Results partially confirmed the hypothesis: while the GAT model showed little to no change in performance without preprocessing, the GCN model experienced a notable decrease in test accuracy, with drops nearing 30% in some runs. For the MLP model, the validation accuracy displayed an intriguing pattern: it would plateau, then jump suddenly at seemingly random epochs, independent of learning rate or preprocessing (Figure 5.5). Removing preprocessing reduced the likelihood of these jumps, leading to poorer overall performance. This suggests that the GAT architecture is the most reliable for effectively learning to separate gestures in latent space, without the need for preprocessing.
2. **Using z Axis Information from Mediapipe Hands:** Although depth information is theoretically beneficial, particularly for recognizing complex finger interactions, as noted in the Kaggle ASL FS Competition data description [6], "the MediaPipe model is not fully trained to predict depth, so you may wish to ignore the z values". Doing so results in a roughly 1% decrease in accuracy, meaning that at least for this study, the component is irrelevant.

3. **Inverse Graph Configuration:** An "inverse graph" structure (Figure 5.7) was also tested, where nodes representing joints not anatomically connected in the hand were linked. Given that anatomically connected joints tend to move in tandem, thus carrying related information in the features, connecting "independent" joints could theoretically increase information flow and improve model performance. This was categorically debunked, as both GNN architectures performed better with the anatomical connections, but GCN consistently felt a bigger drop in end-of-training test accuracy scores.

Figure 5.6: Two methods for connecting hand joints in graph representation

5.5 Optimal Graph

Anatomically connecting the hands is unlikely to be the optimal representation for classifying sign language gestures. Finding such an optimal graph "by hand" is practically impossible, but utilizing the Optimized Graph Convolution Layer (discussed in Section 3.7, there is a way to compute such an optimal connection of hand joints with machine learning. The model learns a weight matrix that represents the weighted graph for the hands. There are practically infinite ways to set up the training process, but to stay comparable to previous GNN architectures, a fixed budget of 100 epochs was used along with 32 as the hidden layer size, similarly to the small models in section 5.2. The following training strategies were tested:

1. **Baseline GCN:** Adjacency Matrix is constructed with anatomical connections and stays constant during training.
2. **Fine-tuning:** 50% GCN training and 50% fine-tuning the adjacency matrix parameter.
3. **Iterative:** Similar to "fine-tuning", but switch every 10 epochs.
4. **Full:** Training the whole network, including the adjacency matrix parameter. Two variants include initialization with anatomical connections and random Kaiming uniform.

Table 5.2: Small optimized GCN convolution comparison by test accuracy

Strategy	1 Layer	2 Layers	3 Layers
Baseline GCN	75.00%	83.74%	89.38%
Fine-tuning	77.85%	93.47%	94.27%
Iterative	90.17%	95.28%	96.67%
Full (anatomical)	90.31%	96.26%	97.10%
Full (random)	91.02%	96.36%	97.32%

5.5.1 Semantic Analysis of Optimal GCN Convolution

As mentioned before, one of the trainable parameters of the Optimal GCN Conv. Architecture (3.14) represents the normalized adjacency matrix in regular GCN layers. After training, it will most definitely not be symmetrical, but by averaging the weights of directed edges that correspond to a single edge in the undirected

version of the graph, a visual representation can be computed of the "optimal" hand graph connections.

With the experimental setup discussed at the beginning of the chapter, it turns out that if the model contains more than 1 layer and training starts with frozen weights to the adjacency matrix parameters, then the model quickly adapts to the given "graph edges" and only minor adjustments happen during the fine-tuning phase. In other cases, no general trends were noticed, and the results look seemingly random.

Figure 5.7: Visualization of the optimal connections for single-layer models with an iterative training strategy. Color saturation represents the absolute magnitude of connection weights. (For visual clarity, weights below the 0.2 magnitude threshold were suppressed.)

5.6 Dynamic Gesture Recognition

In ASL Fingerspelling, the letters 'j' and 'z' require hand movement, where the user draws the letters in the air with specific fingers. They can't be told apart by simply looking at the hand shapes, as they match the gestures used by the letters 'i' and 'd'. There are many simple heuristics to conquer this challenge. One of which is to collect and store the coordinates of the fingertips used to draw the shapes and interpret the result as a black and white image. Simple image classification models can be applied afterwards. The main problem with this approach is that the direction of the movement can't be asserted. To address this, the data must be interpreted as time series sequences, with features being the coordinate values of the hand landmarks over time. The proposed algorithm matches pre-recorded samples with the current user's movement and quantifies how similar they are.

A primary challenge in this task is the variability in signing speed across users, which renders simple point-wise distance metrics ineffective. The algorithm that helps match sequences of different lengths and temporal alignment is *Dynamic Time Warping* (DTW), which computes the optimal alignment path between two time series by warping the temporal axis to minimize distance while preserving the sequence order. For example, two users might perform the same ASL gesture with slightly different timing, one more slowly, the other more quickly. DTW compensates for this by aligning semantically equivalent points, even if they occur at different timestamps.

Algorithm 1: Dynamic Time Warping

Input: Sequences $A = [a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n]$, $B = [b_1, b_2, \dots, b_m]$

Output: DTW distance

```

1 Initialize cost matrix  $D \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$  with  $D(1, 1) = d(a_1, b_1)$  ;
2 for  $i \leftarrow 2$  to  $n$  do
3    $D(i, 1) \leftarrow d(a_i, b_1) + D(i - 1, 1)$  ;
4 for  $j \leftarrow 2$  to  $m$  do
5    $D(1, j) \leftarrow d(a_1, b_j) + D(1, j - 1)$  ;
6 for  $i \leftarrow 2$  to  $n$  do
7   for  $j \leftarrow 2$  to  $m$  do
8      $cost \leftarrow d(a_i, b_j)$  ;
9      $D(i, j) \leftarrow cost + \min(D(i - 1, j), D(i, j - 1), D(i - 1, j - 1))$  ;
10 return  $D(n, m)$ 

```

The algorithm builds a cost matrix that stores the minimum alignment cost at each point and computes the optimal path through this matrix using dynamic programming. This path represents the best mapping between the two sequences under temporal distortion.

Using this distance metric, classification is performed by identifying the sample within a reference set that yields the lowest DTW distance. Although the algorithm supports sequences of multidimensional feature vectors, these experiments focused specifically on the x-coordinates of index finger tips for simplicity.

Validated against a dataset of over 100 self-recorded gestures (split evenly between 'z' and 'j' movements), the approach proved robust. While a limited reference set resulted in rare misclassifications, utilizing the full dataset reduced these instances to only two. This indicates that a sufficiently large sample size can effectively distinguish between distinct movement patterns.

Figure 5.8: Aligned sequences of index finger tips' X coordinate. ('j' on the top and 'z' on the bottom) The sequences are differenced, as the original coordinates may vary with hand placement inside the camera frame.

However, despite potential for fine-tuning, this method remains a heuristic workaround requiring manually distinct gestures. To achieve a production-ready solution capable of modeling the complex sequential nature of sign language, Deep Learning offers a more fundamental approach, which will be explored in the following chapter.

Chapter 6

Sequential Fingerspelling

Earlier experiments (Chapter 5), on the Static Fingerspelling subtask, showed that the new GNN-based embedding layer improved the separation of gestures in latent space representation. However, it remains to be seen whether this embedding technique can enhance the performance of the transformer architecture [45]. Addressing this question is critical, as sign language translation primarily involves sequential tasks.

6.1 Dataset

The dataset, created through a Kaggle competition sponsored by Google [6], aims to translate ASL fingerspelling into text. It includes over three million fingerspelled characters recorded by more than 100 Deaf ASL users from across the United States. Each participant, using a smartphone with a data collection app, was shown English phrases to fingerspell. They controlled video recording by pressing an on-screen button, and though video boundaries were adjusted, some inaccuracies remain. The dataset captures diverse signers across various lighting conditions, backgrounds, and hand preferences, with some even switching hands between clips. Additionally, co-articulation, a natural blending of letter handshapes, and unique approaches to capitalization are reflected, though target phrases are provided in lowercase.

Preprocessing steps:

1. Exclude sequences, including: ”: _ ? = % @ , & ~ () \$ ' ! # [* ; ” characters that are not part of the extended ASL Alphabet (Figure 4.1). These signs only appear in a minority of cases and also lack consensus on their representation.
2. Select the dominant hand, which is the one that appears on more frames.

3. Filter frames that cut off some joints of the previously selected hand.
4. Remove the extensive number of outlier sequences as revealed by the long-tailed distribution (Figure 6.1). Sequences are removed that don't have at least 3 frames/sign or more than 20. (Note that the number of signs is precisely known from the phrase that the signers tried to recreate with gestures, as there is a one-to-one mapping between members of the alphabet and gestures. It is also true in the special case of repeating letters, where signers have to use distinct manual markers [41].)
5. Limit dataset to sequences shorter than 128.
6. The same normalization steps were applied as for the Static Fingerspelling Dataset described in Section 5.1.

Figure 6.1: Distribution of captured frames/sign (max: 67)

6.2 Training and Evaluation

Using the premises of Chapter 5 (Static Fingerspelling), the graph representation of hands will be constructed with anatomically connected joints, where node features include only x and y dimensions returned by the MediaPipe Hands pose approximation model. The embedding layers to compare include the two best-performing GNN models from Chapter 5 and the Convolution-based solution from my previous work discussed in Section 4.2.

The models are trained for 100 epochs each with the batch size limited to 32 for reasons discussed in Section 4.3.2. The model parameters were set according to Table 6.1. For evaluation, two key metrics were used:

Table 6.1: Global settings for transformer model training

Transformer Parameters	Value
hidden dim	128
features/node	2 (x, y)
attention heads	2
# encoder layers	2
# decoder layers	4

1. **Accuracy** was calculated using teacher forcing.
2. **Masked Levenstein Distance**, which cuts off the sequences at the first "End of Sequence" token (EOS) and only compares the "valid" parts of both generated and expected output sequences.

At first, no learning rate scheduler was applied, only the Adam optimizer with the default learning rate of 0.001. The model equipped with the convolutional embedding layer, however, didn't converge using these settings. After applying a custom learning rate scheduler suggested by the original authors of the transformer architecture [45], the model finally started learning.

Figure 6.2: Applied learning rate scheduling: the model with convolutional embedding benefited more from a **linear warmup** strategy, but the GNN architectures performed best, with a **constant learning rate** at the start. **Inverse square root decay** helped all models learn at later epochs.

Results are similar to Static Fingerspelling, with GAT outperforming both other solutions, with a 76.19% test set accuracy compared to the 73.85% by the GCN equipped transformer and 72.44% by the model from the previous study. The application of GGNs once again proved to be more stable when it comes to different hyperparameters.

Figure 6.3: Validation accuracies during transformer training

Table 6.2: Performance comparison of different transformer approaches.

Metric	Conv	GCN	GAT
Acc.	72.44%	73.85%	76.19%
Bal. Acc.	66.58%	68.76%	71.11%
Lev	4.6	4.71	4.47
CPU (avg. ms)	20	762	1110
GPU (avg. ms)	12	24	33
Params	1292968	906408	956712
Embed Par.	419968	33408	83712

The only thing left to compare is the inference speeds. This is particularly important in the case of sequential translation as the model cumulatively generates the output, and a single translation takes several model runs to complete. Inference time was averaged over 100 iterations for each transformer equipped with different embedding algorithms. From the data seen in Table 6.2, it is evident that running the GNN-based models on the CPU is simply not feasible with Pytorch-style mini-batching (3.6). Potential upgrades include applying the optimized GCN Convolution layers discussed in Section 3.7. Nevertheless, utilizing a GPU makes all model configurations feasible for real-time translation.

Chapter 7

Pose Approximation

Pose estimation is the task of estimating the spatial configuration of key points from visual input such as images or video frames. The algorithms are mainly general and can work on a variety of entities, such as the human body, including hands.

Two main methodological paradigms are commonly used in this domain:

1. **Top-down approaches:** A detector model is first employed to identify and crop individual entities within a scene and optionally apply a transform. A dedicated pose estimator is then applied to each detected region to predict the joint locations. This strategy typically yields high per-entity accuracy but relies heavily on the quality of the detection stage while also being computationally expensive in multi-entity settings.
2. **Bottom-up approaches:** These methods bypass the detection step by directly detecting all keypoints in an image simultaneously. The detected joints are subsequently grouped into individual figures based on spatial or associative relationships. This approach scales efficiently with the number of objects in the image, though accurate grouping can be challenging under occlusions or complex interactions.

7.1 General Architecture

Modern pose approximation models typically follow a modular architecture comprising 3 distinct, sequentially connected parts. The **backbone** serves as the primary feature extractor, converting raw image pixels into hierarchical feature maps that capture both low-level textures and high-level semantic information. Backbones

are often initialized with weights pretrained on large-scale datasets to leverage general visual representations and accelerate convergence. Common backbone designs include convolutional neural networks and transformer-based architectures.

The **neck** sits between the backbone and head to further process and integrate the extracted features. It may perform multi-scale feature fusion, channel dimension adjustment, or contextual enhancement to provide richer and more discriminative representations for the downstream task. The neck is optional in some designs, but is particularly beneficial when combining features from multiple resolutions or when enhancing the global context is important.

The **head** is the task-specific module responsible for converting the refined feature maps into final joint predictions. It interprets the information provided by the backbone and neck to produce outputs suitable for the pose estimation task. The choice of head depends on the target application, but they generally follow one of three main formulations:

1. **Heatmap-based heads**, which predict a probability distribution over image coordinates for each keypoint, providing spatial precision and robustness to small localization errors.
2. **Keypoint-based heads**, which directly estimate continuous joint coordinates, resulting in a more compact representation and faster inference but typically lower spatial accuracy.
3. **Vector-field or associative embedding heads**, which output feature fields encoding both keypoint positions and relationships between them, enabling joint grouping in bottom-up frameworks.

Sometimes a final post-processing is also applied, e.g., to produce the final keypoint predictions from heatmaps. This modular design allows pose approximation systems to balance accuracy, efficiency, and scalability depending on the application requirements.

7.2 Model Selection

Utilizing graph-based machine learning in top-down models has dominated studies in recent years:

- **PoseGraphNet++** [8], for example, applies edge convolution on top of node-wise operations to uplift 2D positional information into 3D. The study sets

seeds for the intuition that graphs are also suitable to represent bone-related features, such as bone orientation, while showing state-of-the-art performance on benchmark datasets such as Human3.6M[25].

- Another remarkable study, **Pose Anything** [24] shows that the task for pose recognition can be category-agnostic. The model utilizes minimal support images with annotated keypoints, yet outperforms task-specific approaches, marking a significant advancement in the field. The significance of graph neural networks in the task of pose approximation is already clear, so the goal of the following ablation study is to measure the impact of such networks under experimental conditions.

This case study aims to measure the effects of using Graph Neural Networks instead of regular Deep Learning Components.

7.2.1 Keypoint Models

In keypoint-based settings, the network predicts all keypoints as a vector $x \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times F}$. To ensure comparability across models, a ResNet-18 backbone [23] was used consistently, followed by a linear neck $f_{\text{neck}} : \mathbb{R}^{F'} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{N \times F}$.

In the experiments, a head composed of linear layers was compared to the optimized graph algorithm in Equation 3.14, using the “Full (random)” training strategy described in Section 5.5. Each layer directly updates the (x, y) coordinates, and residual connections were applied in both architectures.

7.2.2 Heatmap Models

Even though heatmap models also produce keypoints at the end, they differ fundamentally from direct-regression approaches by predicting a dense spatial probability distribution for every joint. Concretely, the model outputs K heatmaps $H^{\text{pred}} \in \mathbb{R}^{K \times N \times H' \times W'}$, where each channel corresponds to a single keypoint and encodes its likelihood over a downsampled spatial grid. In the conducted experiments, these heatmaps operate at a quarter of the input resolution, providing a balance between spatial precision and computational efficiency.

To generate these heatmaps, ResNet-18 backbone [23] was again employed similarly to the experiments with Keypoint models, so that results remain comparable, but as in common heatmap-based architectures, the final global pooling and the fully

connected layers are removed. Instead, the backbone serves purely as a feature extractor that produces a compact spatial representation suitable for dense prediction. On top of this feature map, a lightweight extension progressively upsamples the representation back toward higher spatial dimensions. It begins with a convolutional block that adapts the backbone’s output to a fixed intermediate channel width. This is followed by a sequence of transposed convolution layers, each doubling the spatial resolution while refining the underlying features through normalization and nonlinearity. After several upsampling stages, a final 1×1 convolution transforms the features into K output channels, one for each keypoint.

To apply backpropagation, a Gaussian ground truth map was generated according to the following Equation:

$$H_k^{gt}(x, y) = \exp\left(-\frac{(x - x_k)^2 + (y - y_k)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \Big|_{\sigma=1.5} \quad (7.1)$$

For calculating loss, MSE can be directly applied and averaged over all K heatmaps, however, for a probabilistic approach, the Kullback–Leibler Divergence Loss was used after normalizing to a probability distribution:

$$P_k(x, y) = \frac{\exp\left(H_k^{pred}(x, y)\right)}{\sum_{x'=1}^{Width} \sum_{y'=1}^{Height} \exp\left(H_k^{pred}(x', y')\right)}, \quad P_k^{gt} = \frac{H_k^{gt}}{\sum_{i,j} H_k^{gt}(i, j)} \quad (7.2)$$

$$L_{KL} = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{x,y} P_k^{gt}(x, y) \log \frac{P_k^{gt}(x, y)}{P_k(x, y)} \quad (7.3)$$

Two strategies are applied in this study to extract the keypoint coordinates: **argmax** (Equation 7.4) and **softargmax** (Equation 7.5).

$$(x_k, y_k) = \arg \max_{x,y} H_k^{pred}(x, y) \quad (7.4)$$

$$P = \text{softmax}(H^{pred}), \quad x_k = \sum_{x,y} x \cdot P_k(x, y), \quad y_k = \sum_{x,y} y \cdot P_k(x, y) \quad (7.5)$$

The differentiability of softargmax makes it possible to construct a new family of **Hybrid models**, that apply the function directly followed by another head of Linear and GNN Conv layers, similarly to Keypoint models from Section 7.2.1.

7.3 Freihand Dataset

All conducted trainings will be computed with the Freihand [12] dataset, where only the 224×224 cropped RGB image data is used to predict pixel space 2D coordinates in a top-down pose approximation approach. The dataset boasts 32560 unique training samples and 3 times as many artificially modified versions to improve generalization against different backgrounds, while the evaluation set comprises nearly 4000 more complex images.

7.3.1 Metrics

To measure the models, the following metrics were applied in pixel space, with a fixed tolerance threshold τ . The calculations for single instances are averaged over the total number of samples S , each containing N keypoints.

Percentage of Correct Keypoints, where each keypoint is counted as correct if its Euclidean error is below a threshold τ .

$$\text{PCK}(\tau) = \frac{1}{S \cdot N} \sum_{s=1}^S \sum_{i=1}^N \mathbf{1}(\|\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{s,i} - \mathbf{x}_{s,i}\|_2 < \tau) \quad (7.6)$$

Mean Per Joint Position Error is the mean Euclidean distance between predicted and true joints.

$$\text{MPJPE} = \frac{1}{S \cdot N} \sum_{s=1}^S \sum_{i=1}^N \|\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{s,i} - \mathbf{x}_{s,i}\|_2 \quad (7.7)$$

Perfect Poses, where perfect means *all* joints in a sample s are within threshold τ .

$$\text{PP}(\tau) = \frac{1}{S} \sum_{s=1}^S \mathbf{1}\left(\max_i \|\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{s,i} - \mathbf{x}_{s,i}\|_2 < \tau\right) \quad (7.8)$$

Average-Perfect Poses, where a pose counts if its *average* joint error is below τ .

$$\text{A-PP}(\tau) = \frac{1}{S} \sum_{s=1}^S \mathbf{1}\left(\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \|\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{s,i} - \mathbf{x}_{s,i}\|_2 < \tau\right) \quad (7.9)$$

In pose approximation models, it is customary to utilize either raw pixel space coordinates ($x, y \in [0, W - 1]$) or normalized device coordinates (typically in the range $[-1, 1]$) to maintain numerical stability during optimization. However, relying

exclusively on pixel-wise metrics introduces scale ambiguity; the magnitude of a pixel error is depth-dependent, meaning a deviation in screen space for a proximal hand represents a different physical distance than for a distant one. Consequently, pixel metrics are strictly valid only when the subject distance is constant across the dataset. While the Freihand dataset maintains roughly uniform hand placement, it also provides the intrinsic camera matrix and a reference bone length. After 2D pose approximation, these parameters allow for the projection back into metric space by utilizing the known depth values, facilitating the calculation of error in absolute real-world units.

7.3.2 Coordinate Space Transformations

To evaluate the model within real-world units, the projection operation must be inverted. The relationship between the 3D camera coordinates, defined as the vector $\mathbf{P} = [X, Y, Z]^\top$, and the 2D projected pixel coordinates, defined as $\mathbf{p} = [u, v]^\top$, is governed by the pinhole camera model via the intrinsic matrix K :

$$K = \begin{bmatrix} f_x & 0 & c_x \\ 0 & f_y & c_y \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (7.10)$$

Here:

- f_x and f_y represent the focal lengths in horizontal and vertical pixel units, respectively.
- c_x and c_y denote the principal point (optical center) of the image.

The forward projection mapping 3D camera space to 2D pixel space is given by:

$$u = f_x \frac{X}{Z} + c_x, \quad v = f_y \frac{Y}{Z} + c_y \quad (7.11)$$

However, since model predictions are confined to pixel space, the absolute scale is inherently ambiguous. To reconstruct the estimated 3D position $\hat{\mathbf{P}}$ in camera space, the predicted coordinates must be back-projected using the ground truth Z coordinates. In matrix form, utilizing homogeneous coordinates, this back-projection is expressed as:

$$\hat{\mathbf{P}} = Z_{\text{gt}} \cdot K^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{u} \\ \hat{v} \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (7.12)$$

Computing Euclidean distance-based metrics with the projected coordinates is possible using the reference scale of the proximal phalangeal bone of the middle finger provided by the dataset.

Table 7.1: Performance on the Freihand evaluation dataset after 30 epochs with distance threshold (τ)

Model	Size	MPJPE	τ	PCK	PP	A-PP
Keypoint Linear	11,732,889	43.82 px 45.58 mm	5 px	23.59%	0.00%	6.82%
			10 px	54.38%	4.32%	46.74%
			10 mm	35.97%	0.15%	20.15%
			15 mm	55.02%	4.27%	48.48%
Keypoint GNN	11,736,972	41.71 px 42.85 mm	5 px	25.23%	0.03%	8.28%
			10 px	56.98%	5.86%	50.39%
			10 mm	38.16%	0.78%	22.93%
			15 mm	57.77%	6.01%	52.57%
Hybrid GNN	15,511,692	36.25 px 36.71 mm	5 px	36.10%	0.89%	19.43%
			10 px	67.78%	13.39%	65.08%
			10 mm	50.60%	2.98%	39.27%
			15 mm	68.61%	13.76%	66.16%
Heatmap	15,510,357	36.98 px 37.34 mm	5 px	40.23%	0.99%	23.02%
			10 px	71.12%	16.33%	67.84%
			10 mm	54.78%	3.89%	43.11%
			15 mm	71.99%	16.62%	68.76%
Mediapipe ¹	$\sim 2,100,000^2$	33.37 px 25.68 mm	5 px	39.56%	0.24%	22.30%
			10 px	72.86%	17.03%	73.87%
			10 mm	69.16%	8.62%	69.69%
			15 mm	83.96%	37.80%	87.26%

7.4 Conclusion

Based on the results of earlier chapters (Chapter 5), intuition suggests that GNN layers should be more effective at refining the keypoints predicted by the neck, but Table 7.1 reveals, there is no significant difference. While the GNN head improved performance for the keypoint models by a little, the same trick didn't improve the best-performing model using heatmaps. It is hypothesized that the main bottleneck is that the GNN layers only receive the scarce features of presumed x, y coordinates, instead of a dense feature vector encoding visual information. Potential improvements also include applying anatomical constraints to loss functions to punish impossible joint angles and bone lengths.

Comparing these custom models to Mediapipe[21], it is evident that the Google solution outperforms all of them, although it must be noted that, despite using their best model with minimum detection confidence, it failed to detect hands on 248 images, which were not reflected in the metrics. The advantage is further increased with tight Android integration, parameter efficiency, and optimized tracking capabilities for sequential frames [21]. Based on this evaluation, in the following Android Integration Chapter, the Mediapipe Model will be applied.

¹The analysis was performed using package version 0.10.21, configured with a complexity setting of one and minimal confidence thresholds. Due to the multi-stage design, hands were not detected in 248 images, and these instances were excluded from the final metrics.

²This framework is composed of multiple neural networks; the number [40] describes specifically the pose approximation component.

Chapter 8

Android Integration

The motivation for deploying graph-based models on Android stems from the goal of enabling accessible, real-time American Sign Language (ASL) fingerspelling learning and data collection through a mobile application. By leveraging models such as hand pose estimation and skeletal tracking, the app can capture and process user gestures on-device efficiently, ensuring low-latency feedback and offline usability. The pose data, represented as compact graph structures, can be stored in a space-efficient format and synchronized with a remote database for further analysis or training. This enables both an interactive learning experience and a scalable collection of annotated sign language data, supporting the broader objective of improving sign language technologies and educational tools.

Given the current state of the technology, the sequential fingerspelling models developed in this study are best suited for experienced, fast signers, where distinct or 'clean' frames are rare. In contrast, static fingerspelling remains superior for slow-paced signing, where individual signs are held longer. Furthermore, the high parameter efficiency of static models makes them ideal for deployment in hardware-restricted environments. This chapter details the practical implementation of such models via the **SignBuddy** application, a modern Android system designed to operate within these resource constraints. Built upon a robust and maintainable multi-layered architecture, the application's core sign recognition feature implements a data flow pipeline connecting the camera's landmark detection output with the machine learning inference engine and the UI layer. Each frame of the detected hand landmarks is preprocessed, passed through a TensorFlow Lite (TFLite) model for inference, and recognized signs are propagated via reactive state flows to update the user interface in real time.

8.1 Architecture

The application integrates key architectural patterns and Android best practices, including Jetpack Compose for declarative UI design, the Model-View-Intent (MVI) architectural pattern for unidirectional state management, Hilt for dependency injection, and feature-first modularization to promote scalability and separation of concerns.

Each feature follows a clean, layered architecture:

1. **Presentation Layer:** Responsible for UI logic and user interactions, implemented with Jetpack Compose and ViewModels using reactive state management.
2. **Domain Layer:** Contains use cases and business logic, such as saving recorded landmark sequences.
3. **Data Layer:** Handles persistence and data access. In the recognition flow, most data originates from real-time input rather than external repositories.

This structure enhances both **testability** and **maintainability**. The domain layer remains independent of Android framework classes, while the presentation layer manages state transitions through observable flows, ensuring predictable and reactive UI updates.

8.1.1 Model-View-Intent Pattern

The Model-View-Intent (MVI) pattern forms the backbone of SignBuddy's presentation logic. MVI enforces unidirectional data flow, making UI states explicit, reproducible, and easy to debug. In the recognition module, the `LandmarkRecordingViewModel` orchestrates this loop by mediating between user actions, domain logic, and UI rendering. To ensure deterministic behavior and eliminate inconsistent states, as the name suggests, the architecture is divided into three distinct components:

1. **Model:** Represented by `LandmarkRecordingState`, this data class holds the complete UI state, including recording status, recognized characters, inference confidence, and the recorded landmark list.
2. **View:** Observes state updates via `StateFlow<LandmarkRecordingState>` and automatically re-composes the UI whenever new values are emitted.

3. **Intent:** Defined by the sealed class `LandmarkEvent`, this describes all possible actions, such as toggling recording or receiving a new recognized frame.

8.2 MediaPipe Hands on Android

Developed by Google, MediaPipe is a cross-platform framework optimized for real-time mobile machine learning pipelines. It utilizes a graph-based architecture [34] to orchestrate prebuilt perception models. MediaPipe Hands [51] specifically enables high-fidelity gesture recognition by chaining a lightweight palm detector with a landmark model that regresses 21 3D keypoints per hand. On Android, the framework maximizes inference speed by leveraging native C++ libraries and GPU acceleration via OpenGL ES.

8.2.1 Integration with Jetpack Compose

Implementing real-time computer vision pipelines within modern Android development introduces specific architectural challenges, particularly when utilizing Jetpack Compose. While MediaPipe offers robust inference capabilities, the official Android integration relies on imperative state management, whereas Jetpack Compose operates on a declarative UI paradigm. A primary difficulty arises from the dependency of the CameraX library on the Android View system, specifically the `PreviewView` component, which is not natively compatible with the composable hierarchy. Furthermore, managing the lifecycle of the camera provider, image analysis, and the MediaPipe graph asynchronously within a recomposing UI requires careful orchestration to prevent memory leaks and frame processing latency.

To address these complexities, a modular architecture was adopted. The lower-level interactions with the MediaPipe library were encapsulated within a dedicated wrapper class, `HandLandmarkerHelper`. This class abstracts the initialization of the MediaPipe framework, manages the selection of computational delegates (CPU or GPU), and handles the conversion of `ImageProxy` objects from the camera into objects required by the model. By isolating these logic operations, the UI layer remains agnostic to the underlying inference mechanics.

```

1 class GestureRecognizerBuilder(
2     private val onResult: (Landmark) -> Unit = { }
3 ) {
4     private lateinit var handLandmarkerHelper: HandLandmarkerHelper
5
6     @Composable
7     fun Build(modifier: Modifier = Modifier) {
8         val context = LocalContext.current
9         val lifecycleOwner = androidx.lifecycle.compose.LocalLifecycleOwner.current
10        val previewView = remember { PreviewView(context) }
11
12        // Asynchronous camera initialization
13        LaunchedEffect(Unit) {
14            handLandmarkerHelper = HandLandmarkerHelper(
15                context = context,
16                runningMode = RunningMode.LIVE_STREAM,
17                onResults = { resultBundle ->
18                    val detectionResult = resultBundle.results[0]
19                    // ... logic to update UI or OverlayView ...
20                }
21            )
22
23            val preview = Preview.Builder()
24                .setTargetRotation(previewView.display.rotation)
25                .build()
26
27            val imageAnalyzer = ImageAnalysis.Builder()
28                .setBackpressureStrategy(ImageAnalysis.STRATEGY_KEEP_ONLY_LATEST)
29                .setOutputImageFormat(ImageAnalysis.OUTPUT_IMAGE_FORMAT_RGBA_8888)
30                .build()
31                .also {
32                    it.setAnalyzer(
33                        ContextCompat.getMainExecutor(context),
34                        handLandmarkerHelper::detectLiveStream
35                    )
36                }
37
38            val cameraProvider = context.getCameraProvider()
39            cameraProvider.unbindAll()
40            cameraProvider.bindToLifecycle(
41                lifecycleOwner,
42                CameraSelector.DEFAULT_FRONT_CAMERA,
43                preview,
44                imageAnalyzer
45            )
46
47            preview.surfaceProvider = previewView.surfaceProvider
48        }
49
50        // Interoperability with AndroidView
51        Box(contentAlignment = Alignment.Center) {
52            AndroidView(factory = { previewView })
53            // ... OverlayView ...
54        }
55    }
56 }

```

Listing 8.1: CameraX image analysis integration within Jetpack Compose

The bridge between the imperative CameraX API and the declarative UI was established using the `AndroidView` composable. This interoperability container allows the `PreviewView` to be instantiated and attached to the Compose node hierarchy. As demonstrated in Listing 8.2, the `ProcessCameraProvider` is explicitly bound to the `LocalLifecycleOwner`. This ensures that camera resources, including the preview stream and the `ImageAnalysis` use case, are allocated and released in strict synchronization with the composable’s lifecycle.

The `ImageAnalysis` use case was configured with a non-blocking strategy (`STRATEGY_KEEP_ONLY_LATEST`) to ensure that the inference pipeline does not become a bottleneck for the UI rendering. Frames are extracted, formatted to RGBA, and passed to the helper class for detection, with results subsequently utilized to update a custom overlay view for real-time visualization.

8.3 Deep Learning Model Serialization for Mobile Inference

The deployment of self-trained deep neural networks on mobile platforms such as Android needs efficient serialization formats that balance fidelity, inference latency, and memory footprint. Serialization, in this context, refers to the transformation of a trained model into a compact, portable representation that can be executed by a lightweight runtime on resource-constrained devices. This section provides a scientific overview of two widely adopted model serialization formats for mobile inference: TensorFlow Lite (TFLite) and Open Neural Network Exchange (ONNX).

8.3.1 TensorFlow Lite

TensorFlow Lite (TFLite) is a model format and runtime specifically designed for deploying TensorFlow models on edge devices, particularly those running Android. TFLite models are serialized using the FlatBuffers binary format, which is optimized for low-latency parsing and in-place memory access without requiring deserialization. This contrasts with formats such as Protocol Buffers, which typically incur additional parsing overhead.

TFLite models are generated using the `TFLiteConverter`, which transforms a trained TensorFlow model (e.g., a `SavedModel` or Keras model) into a static computation graph compatible with the TFLite runtime. During conversion, the model graph is pruned, control flow is statically resolved, and unsupported operations

are either removed or replaced with supported equivalents. Crucially, TFLite supports post-training quantization and quantization-aware training, enabling models to be converted from 32-bit floating-point to 8-bit integer representations. These quantization techniques reduce model size and improve inference performance on ARM-based CPUs, while maintaining acceptable accuracy for many use cases.

The TFLite runtime on Android leverages XNNPACK for optimized CPU inference and supports hardware acceleration via the Android Neural Networks API (NNAPI), GPU delegates, and vendor-specific NPUs. The resulting TFLite model is platform-independent, with a significant file size reduction of up to 4× when quantized, and offers deterministic inference behavior, which is essential for safety-critical applications.

8.3.2 Open Neural Network Exchange (ONNX)

The Open Neural Network Exchange (ONNX) format provides a standardized and extensible intermediate representation (IR) for deep learning models. Originally co-developed by Microsoft and Facebook, ONNX aims to enable interoperability between different machine learning frameworks, including PyTorch, TensorFlow, and Caffe2. ONNX models are serialized using Protocol Buffers (protobuf) and encapsulate a computation graph consisting of tensor operations and model metadata.

In practical Android pipelines, ONNX is often used as a transitional format, particularly when converting models trained in PyTorch to formats supported by mobile runtimes such as TensorFlow Lite. The conversion path (e.g., PyTorch → ONNX → TensorFlow → TFLite) introduces several challenges, including differences in dynamic/static graph semantics, operator availability, and numerical precision. These challenges require rigorous post-conversion validation and may necessitate custom operator implementations or graph rewriting to achieve compatibility. In this study, models were trained in PyTorch, so conversion seemed appropriate with this method, but the official ONNX to TensorFlow conversion library is not actively maintained by the ONNX Steering Committee, and sadly, it didn't work for this exact use case due to a version mismatch problem and deprecated library codes.

Microsoft offers an Android ONNX Runtime that allows these models to run directly on Android, but the GPU acceleration, provided via NNAPI, has been declared deprecated since Android 15 [4]. It seems like Google is pushing everyone towards the TFLite format, but a method for easy, inter-framework model conversion remains elusive. Currently, the best option for conversion is using Google's highly work-in-

progress ai-edge-torch Python package, which can convert specifically structured torch models to TFLite.

8.3.3 Optimized GCN Serialization

Due to the complexity and lack of support, ONNX conversion was left behind, and the Optimized GCN model was reimplemented in Tensorflow instead of PyTorch. Basic conversion between TensorFlow and TFLite is straightforward, but there was a technical challenge with producing a GPU Delegate Ready model. The problem occurs during the computation of $\hat{A} \times X$, where:

- $X \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times N \times F}$ is the batch of node feature matrices, with B batches, N nodes, and F features per node.
- $\hat{A} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$ is the normalized adjacency matrix.

The issue is that X , as a batch of node features triggers an automatic `BatchMatMul` operation, which is not supported by the Android GPU delegate in TensorFlow Lite at the moment [22]. The solution is to manually broadcast the adjacency matrix and node feature matrix, then apply element-wise multiplication and summation:

1. Expand \hat{A} with a batch dimension and add a trailing singleton dimension to align with feature dimension:

$$\hat{A} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N} \quad \rightarrow \quad \hat{A}_{\text{exp}} \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times N \times N \times 1} \quad (8.1)$$

2. Expand X to match adjacency dimensions for broadcasting:

$$X \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times N \times F} \quad \rightarrow \quad X_{\text{exp}} \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times 1 \times N \times F} \quad (8.2)$$

3. Element-wise multiply with broadcasting:

$$M = \hat{A}_{\text{exp}} \odot X_{\text{exp}} \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times N \times N \times F} \quad (8.3)$$

4. Sum over the shared node dimension (axis=2) to aggregate neighbors:

$$AX = \sum_{j=1}^N M[:, :, j, :] \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times N \times F} \quad (8.4)$$

The takeaway is that model conversion, especially if certain operations are restricted, is currently a half-manual process, and models must be constructed with the target platform and framework in mind.

Figure 8.1: Final TFLite model visualization

8.4 Sign Recognition Pipeline

The integration of the TFLite model is architected as a reactive, unidirectional data flow. This design ensures that the high-frequency data generation from the camera does not impede the user interface rendering. The communication pipeline relies on a strict separation of concerns between the UI layer, the state holder, and the inference helper.

The process is initiated within the UI layer, namely the `GestureRecognizerTile` component, where hand landmarks are detected, as illustrated in Listing 8.2. Upon the detection of a hand, the result is encapsulated in a `LandmarkRecordingEvent` and immediately dispatched to the `ViewModel`.

```

1 // Inside LandmarkRecordingScreen.kt
2 GestureRecognizerTile(
3     onResult = { landmark ->
4         // The event is triggered, passing the data to the ViewModel
5         viewModel.onEvent(LandmarkRecordingEvent.NewFrameRecognized(landmark))
6     }
7 )

```

Listing 8.2: Propagation of recognized frames from the UI to the ViewModel.

Upon receiving the event, data is processed by the `LandmarkRecordingViewModel`. As shown in Listing 8.3, the ViewModel serves as an intermediary; the landmark data is recorded if the recording state is active, and the inference request is delegated to the `SignRecognitionHelper`.

```

1 // Inside LandmarkRecordingViewModel.kt
2 fun onEvent(event: LandmarkRecordingEvent){
3     when(event){
4         is LandmarkRecordingEvent.NewFrameRecognized -> {
5             if (state.value.isRecording){
6                 _state.update{ it.copy(
7                     recordedLandmarks = it.recordedLandmarks + event.landmark
8                 )}
9             }
10            recognizeGesture(event.landmark)
11        }
12        // ...
13    }
14 }

```

Listing 8.3: Event handling and delegation to the inference helper.

The heavy computational load is managed by the `SignRecognitionHelper`. To ensure optimal performance, hardware acceleration is dynamically selected during initialization. The GPU delegate is prioritized via the `CompatibilityList` API; if unavailable, the system reverts to the CPU or the Android Neural Networks API (NNAPI), as demonstrated in Listing 8.4.

```

1 // Inside SignRecognitionHelper.kt
2 fun initModel(delegate: Delegate = Delegate.GPU) {
3     val compatList = CompatibilityList()
4     val options = Interpreter.Options().apply {
5         if (compatList.isDelegateSupportedOnThisDevice) {
6             addDelegate(GpuDelegate(compatList.bestOptionsForThisDevice))
7         } else {
8             numThreads = 4
9             useNNAPI = delegate == Delegate.NNAPI
10        }
11    }
12    interpreter = Interpreter(litertBuffer, options)
13 }

```

Listing 8.4: Dynamic selection of hardware delegates for the TFLite Interpreter.

To maintain main-thread fluidity, the inference logic is executed asynchronously on the I/O dispatcher. As depicted in Listing 8.5, the raw landmarks are preprocessed, fed into the interpreter, and the results are emitted via a `MutableSharedFlow`. This hot stream mechanism allows for the buffering of results, decoupling the inference speed from the consumption rate.

```

1 // Inside SignRecognitionHelper.kt
2 private val _result = MutableSharedFlow<Result>(
3     extraBufferCapacity = 64, onBufferOverflow = BufferOverflow.DROP_OLDEST
4 )
5 val result: SharedFlow<Result>
6     get() = _result
7
8 suspend fun recognizeGesture(lm: Landmark) {
9     withContext(Dispatchers.IO) {
10         val inputBuffer = preprocess(lm)
11         val outputBuffer = inference(inputBuffer)
12         val (predictedSymbol, confidence) = postProcess(outputBuffer)
13
14         // Results are emitted to the subscriber (Flow -> ViewModel -> UI)
15         _result.emit(
16             Result(
17                 gesture = predictedSymbol,
18                 confidence = confidence
19             )
20         )
21     }
22 }

```

Listing 8.5: Offloading inference to the I/O dispatcher and publishing results.

The cycle is completed within the `ViewModel`, where it exposes the inference results to the UI component, ensuring a clear separation of concerns. A final overview diagram in Figure 8.2 shows the whole data flow process between architectural elements.

Figure 8.2: Sign recognition pipeline communication flow

Chapter 9

Conclusion

In summary, the research successfully achieved its primary objectives, validating the hypotheses through both empirical measurements and the development of a concrete solution. This work demonstrated the feasibility and effectiveness of using Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) for pose data in American Sign Language (ASL) fingerspelling translation, exceeding the performance of prior models. The GNN-based networks surpassed the previously used Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) for static fingerspelling and convolutional embeddings for sequential data, demonstrating enhanced accuracy and adaptability. Specifically, GNNs addressed the limitations of convolutional approaches, such as sequence padding issues and the preservation of semantic structure, providing a robust alternative.

Through extensive experimentation with different model configurations, including variations in depth and hidden layer sizes, the Graph Attention Network (GAT) architecture was found to yield the best results. This model leveraged a custom weighting mechanism for neighboring nodes during message passing, achieving a peak test accuracy of 98.05% for static fingerspelling, substantially higher than the 91.9% accuracy of the MLP model from the previous study [14]. In the context of sequential fingerspelling, the new GAT-based embedding achieved a test accuracy of 76.19%, also outperforming the previous best model, which reached only 72.44%. Sequential graph batching techniques, enabled by PyTorch Geometric, were also pivotal, allowing the GNN model to efficiently scale to larger datasets and preserve spatial information in real time.

In conclusion, this research not only established that pose information can effectively be represented as a graph, but also that GNNs offer a powerful framework for advancing ASL translation tasks, capable of operating with a high degree of parameter efficiency in hardware-constrained environments. The insights and results

of this study provide a foundation for future exploration in graph-based approaches to sign language recognition and other gesture-related applications.

Future Work

- The ever-growing prominence of Large Language Models inspires the question of how well the sequential fingerspelling approach can scale. If similar scaling principles apply [30], this could mark the beginning of a new era of extended large language models. It also invites exploration into whether the GPT architecture could be adapted to solve the challenge of translating graph sequences into text.
- To further demonstrate the superiority of GNN-based embedding layers, it would be beneficial to explore how they can handle missing points in pose approximation data. By leveraging graphs to represent damaged input, we can avoid the use of padding tokens, allowing for a more efficient and accurate representation of incomplete data. This approach not only enhances the model's robustness but also highlights the flexibility of GNNs in managing real-world scenarios where data may be sparse or incomplete.
- Improving pose approximation algorithms is the single most critical factor in advancing sign language translation with Graph Neural Networks. Enhanced models that provide more accurate 3D representations and reliably handle interactions between hands and other body parts are essential. While the methods explored in Chapter 7 didn't improve the current baseline, many recent studies have shown promising progress[26][8][24], which suggests great potential for improvements in the area.
- There are promising results for the reverse task of this study, where animations of sign language gestures are generated from a piece of text [7][5]. By creating diverse gesture animations from textual input, we can enhance the training datasets available for models, ultimately improving their performance and robustness in understanding and interpreting sign language.

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